

Effect of fertilizer and organic manure on ShR intensity and rice grain yield. Kerala, India, 1985.

Treatment	Disease intensity ^a		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Without fungicide (F ₀)	With fungicide (F ₁)	Without fungicide (F ₀)	With fungicide (F ₁)
Organic manure (OM) alone @ 5 t/ha in soil at planting	4.9	3.5	3.0	2.8
OM + N ₁ (urea) and K soil application	6.7	5.0	4.6	4.6
OM + N ₂ (ammonium sulfate) and K soil application	7.5	4.5	4.4	4.5
OM + N ₁ and K, last split of both N and K as foliar sprays	5.9	5.9	4.6	5.0
OM + N ₂ and K, last split of both N and K as foliar sprays	4.1	8.1	4.4	4.6
OM + N ₁ + K + Zn and Mn foliar sprays	8.2	6.1	4.6	4.7
OM + N ₂ + K + Zn and Mn foliar sprays	9.2	6.7	4.4	4.5
LSD for treatment (T)	2.1		197.1	
LSD for T × fungicide	3.0		—	

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice 1 to 9 scale.

45 and 60 d after transplanting.

Five random 1-m² samples were observed in each 24-m² plot. Each hill was scored on type and spread of lesions and on panicle damage. Average score for each plot was taken as disease intensity.

Urea was the best N source for yield; foliar application of N and K along with the fungicidal spray reduced panicle damage (see table).

We concluded that treatment improved the general health of the crop, especially in soils where the rate of absorption becomes poor with crop age. That, in turn, could reduce the rate of grain damage. □

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Greenhouse trials of seed dress method for controlling sheath blight (ShB)

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Rice grain-hull (1:4) culture of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn was incubated for 3-4 wk for use as inoculum. Baked soil was handmixed with the rice grain-hull culture at 3:2, then incubated for 1 wk. The mixture was transferred to plastic basins 18 cm in diameter.

Seed dressing used the slurry method of fungicidal application at 40 g/kg seeds, except 4 g PCNB/kg seeds with water added at 2-3% seed weight. Two days after transfer of incubated soil into the plastic basins, 100 treated seeds were planted. Percentages of germination and seedling infection were recorded 3 wk after planting. Controls were untreated seeds planted on uninfested soil and untreated seeds planted on infested soil. A completely randomized block design was used.

All fungicides tested were effective against *R. solani*, as shown by high

Germination, infection, and height and root length of UPLRi5 seedlings treated with fungicides, using the seed dress method, 21 d after sowing. UPLB, Philippines.

Fungicide	Rate (g/kg seeds)	Germination ^a (%)	Infection ^b (%)	Height ^c (cm)	Root length ^c (cm)
Benomyl	40	92.0 a	0.0 a	21.8	5.4
PCNB	4	95.6 a	0.0 a	22.4	6.2
Iprodione	40	91.3 a	0.0 a	20.6	6.7
EMDOC ^d	40	94.0 a	0.3 a	21.4	5.6
Benomyl-EMDOC	40-40	91.0 a	0.3 a	21.1	6.4
Benomyl-iprodione	40-40	90.3 a	0.0 a	20.9	7.7
EMDOC-iprodione	40-40	89.3 a	0.3 a	19.1	7.9
DHMu ^e - iprodione	40-40	81.6 b	0.4 a	22.5	7.4
Triphenyltin acetate-iprodione	40-40	92.0 a	0.3 a	19.6	4.8
Triphenyltin acetate-EMDOC	40-40	81.3 b	0.3 a	21.1	5.5
Triphenyltin acetate-triphenyltin hydroxide	40-40	81.6 b	1.2 a	18.3	2.9
Untreated seeds, inoculated soil	—	36.6 c	3.5 b	21.2	2.6
Untreated seeds, uninoculated soil	—	87.3 a	0.0 a	20.6	3.4

^aMean of 100 seedlings in 3 replications. ^bMean of 3 replications based on % germination. ^cMean of 15 seedlings used. Means in a column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 1% level. ^dEthyl 3-(3-5-dichloro-phenyl)-5-methyl-2-4-deoxy-5-oxozolidine carboxylate (Serinal 50% WP). ^e1-5-1 (5'-0-carbamoyl-2'' amino 2'' deoxy-L xylonyl)-5''deoxy-B-D (all furanonyluronic acid)-hydroxy-methyl uracil (Polyoxine AWP).

germination percentage and low infestation percentage (see table). Germination was highest with PCNB, lowest in untreated seeds in inoculated soil. No infection was observed with

benomyl, PCNB, iprodione, and benomyl-iprodione combined. Untreated seeds in inoculated soil showed significantly higher infection than all other treatments. □